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ROBERT KADLEC**

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Reflections on A Critical Review of COVID-19 Origins: “Hidden in Plain Sight” by Dr. Robert Kadlec

Alina Chan

How should the origin of a novel pandemic pathogen be investigated? Some investigators like the World Health Organization’s scientific advisory group for the origins of novel pathogens (SAGO) place a premium on peer-reviewed scientific literature. Without access to laboratories in Wuhan, these investigators admit that they cannot assess the possibility of a laboratory origin and are therefore thwarted when a government withholds key information.¹ Some investigators will pull up their fanciest new machine learning model and ask whether there are signs that the pathogen is a laboratory construct – disregarding the fact that scientists have been genetically engineering and synthesizing pathogens without leaving a trace for more than a decade.²

Dr. Robert Kadlec and his team’s multi-year investigation stands out by scrutinizing a wide range of open-source intelligence. As far as I know, Dr. Kadlec’s report is the most exhaustive Covid origins analysis to have come into the open from government efforts in the United States and elsewhere. It demonstrates the type of extensive investigation that we should expect of our governments and international public health organizations in response to a pandemic of ambiguous origin – one that is resourceful and bold, not immediately stymied as soon as the government of the country of origin decides to engage in a cover-up. As renown virologist David Baltimore said, how Covid came about is a question of history.³ Science alone cannot tell us how Covid emerged in Wuhan in 2019. An investigation must determine whether the virus was studied in a laboratory before the detected outbreak. Intelligence collected from human sources, intercepted signals or data, and open-source intelligence may be far more illuminating than peer-reviewed scientific analyses.

Dr. Kadlec’s report concludes that a preponderance of evidence supports a research-related incident over a natural zoonotic outbreak. It summarizes the many arguments, often peer-reviewed, against the hypothesis that Covid spilled over from animals to humans at earliest in late November 2019 at a market in Wuhan. In comparison, WHO’s SAGO believes that the scientific data show the first Covid cases only occurred in early December despite evidence

¹ Scientific Advisory Group for the Origins of Novel Pathogens (SAGO), *Independent Assessment of the Origins of SARS-CoV-2* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2025), https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/documents/epp/sago/independent-assessment-of-the-origins-of-sars-cov-2-by-sago.pdf?sfvrsn=b0f90ad4_4&download=true.

² Sarah Scoles, “How Do We Know If a Virus Is Bioengineered?,” Medium, August 5, 2020, <https://futurehuman.medium.com/how-do-we-know-if-a-virus-is-bioengineered-541ff6f8a48f>.

³ David Baltimore, interview, “The Debate over Origins of SARS-CoV-2,” *The Caltech Weekly*, June 22, 2021, <https://www.caltech.edu/about/news/the-debate-over-origins-of-sars-cov-2>.

that the Chinese authorities have not shared information on dozens of cases extending back to November 2019.^{4,5} Dr. Kadlec's investigation also takes a special interest in the activities and interests of military researchers at the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV). As the Office of the Director of National Intelligence confirmed, the WIV had been collaborating with the Chinese military on coronavirus research and the military had used WIV laboratories for virus research prior to the pandemic.⁶ Just months before the pandemic, U.S. Department of Energy officials reportedly warned a top adviser to Anthony Fauci that the coronavirus research they funded at the WIV risked being misappropriated for military purposes.⁷ So, Dr. Kadlec asks a well-founded question: could Covid have accidentally emerged from clandestine coronavirus research in Wuhan led by or conducted in partnership with the Chinese military?

In 2020, asking this question in public would have gotten you cancelled and categorized as the worst sort of human being. Even as late as November 2021, an award-winning science writer questioned whether it was morally defensible for me to write a book that evaluates the evidence for a natural or laboratory origin of Covid and compared my co-author and I to a Holocaust denier.⁸ So, I am very glad that Dr. Kadlec lays out the evidence that leads him to believe that Chinese military researchers may have been aware of and experimenting with SARS-CoV-2 as early as the summer of 2019. This published analysis at least gives us the opportunity to look at the evidence considered and openly discuss different interpretations.

This is my take. Based on the available evidence, I do not assess that there is any decisive evidence (yet) that Chinese researchers had been studying SARS-CoV-2 prior to the known outbreak. As I wrote in the New York Times, there is ample circumstantial evidence pointing to a laboratory origin but no clear proof yet that researchers had the virus in hand before December 2019.⁹ Dr. Kadlec points to a notable Covid vaccine patent filed in February 2020 by a Chinese military researcher (this scientist was also a WIV collaborator and his premature death in 2020 is shrouded in mystery) as evidence that they must have possessed the virus at latest by November 2019. However, in my opinion, the experiments described in the patent could plausibly have been conducted starting in December 2019 and completed by February 2020. What the patent does show is that Chinese military researchers had perceived the catastrophic potential of Covid and rushed to create a vaccine in the context of a national emergency. Separately, in my opinion, there is not enough evidence to show that SARS-CoV-2 is unique among betacoronaviruses in its ability to cause neurological symptoms. Long Covid is real and there are millions of people

⁴ SAGO, *Independent Assessment*.

⁵ Editorial Board, "Wuhan's Early Covid Cases Are a Mystery. What Is China Hiding?," *Washington Post*, November 17, 2022, <https://www.washingtonpost.com/opinions/2022/11/17/covid-early-cases-wuhan-china-mystery/>.

⁶ Office of the Director of National Intelligence, *Potential Links Between the Wuhan Institute of Virology and the Origins of COVID-19* (Washington, DC: Office of the Director of National Intelligence, 2023), <https://www.dni.gov/files/ODNI/documents/assessments/Report-on-Potential-Links-Between-the-Wuhan-Institute-of-Virology-and-the-Origins-of-COVID-19-20230623.pdf>.

⁷ Katherine Eban, "Secret Warnings About Wuhan Research Predated the Pandemic," *Vanity Fair*, November 21, 2023, <https://www.vanityfair.com/news/2023/11/covid-origins-warnings-nih-department-of-energy>.

⁸ Matt Ridley and Alina Chan, *Viral: The Search for the Origin of Covid-19*, 2nd ed. (New York, NY: HarperCollins, 2022).

⁹ Alina Chan, "Why the Pandemic Probably Started in a Lab, in 5 Key Points," *New York Times*, June 3, 2024, <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2024/06/03/opinion/covid-lab-leak.html>.

still struggling with long Covid. However, there have been billions of Covid infections (many of us have been infected again and again over the past five years) in comparison to only thousands who were infected by the 2003 SARS virus or MERS coronaviruses. Still, there are anecdotal reports of neurological symptoms in some cases of SARS and MERS.^{10,11,12} So, the fact that Covid can cause neurological symptoms in a small fraction of cases does not mean that it was created by a research program focused on viruses that infect the human brain.

These questions of whether and, if so, why researchers were studying SARS-CoV-2 before the outbreak remain unanswered. We may have to wait several decades before a whistleblower can shed light on these questions. In the past five years, despite millions killed by the pandemic, there has not been a thorough investigation of how Covid came to be. Shockingly, close partners of the WIV who reside in the United States and other countries have not been forced to provide the full array of exchanged data and communications. In particular, the EcoHealth Alliance which received several years of U.S. federal funding to hunt for coronaviruses with the WIV was not even subpoenaed.¹³ Several scientists internationally have claimed that the pandemic virus was detected in samples in their country prior to the known outbreak. Why has the WHO not organized a reproducibility study to obtain these samples and verify these claims? There are also several scientists and doctors who claim that they had heard of an unexplained respiratory disease spreading in Wuhan by mid-December 2019. Why has the U.S. government not interviewed these doctors and obtained clear evidence that this is true (which could move the start date of the pandemic earlier in 2019)? Until today, there has not been a full search through U.S. databases to see if early Covid sequences could be present in data deposited by Chinese researchers prior to the detected pandemic. Germany's foreign intelligence service assessed a laboratory origin of Covid with 80 to 95 percent certainty but we do not know what classified intelligence their assessment is based on.¹⁴ At the very least, I hope that the current Director of National Intelligence will declassify more intelligence that the United States possesses according to the Covid-19 Origin Act of 2023.

In the absence of a fuller investigation, there is a worrying number of suspicious incidents and known unknowns, as highlighted by Dr. Kadlec's report, when it comes to the types of research at the WIV, the personnel performing that research, and the viruses they possessed in 2019. In his report, Dr. Kadlec compiles statements by Chinese researchers on hidden sources of pathogen exposures in research laboratories, alongside highly relevant WIV patents, procurements, and recorded concerns prior to the pandemic. These biosafety concerns have been

¹⁰ C. C. Chao et al., "Peripheral Nerve Disease in SARS: Report of a Case," *Neurology* 61, no. 12 (2003): 1820–1821, <https://doi.org/10.1212/01.WNL.0000099171.26943.D0>.

¹¹ Brynne Stainsby et al., "Neuromusculoskeletal Disorders Following SARS: A Case Series," *The Journal of the Canadian Chiropractic Association* 55, no. 1 (2011): 32–39, <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21403780/>.

¹² Jee-Eun Kim et al., "Neurological Complications during Treatment of Middle East Respiratory Syndrome," *Journal of Clinical Neurology* 13, no. 3 (2017): 227–233, <https://doi.org/10.3988/jcn.2017.13.3.227>.

¹³ National Institutes of Health, "Understanding the Risk of Bat Coronavirus Emergence," NIH RePORTER, accessed September 2, 2025, <https://reporter.nih.gov/search/-bvPCvB7zkyvb1AjAgW5Yg/project-details/8674931>.

¹⁴ Franz Becchi, "Berichte: Corona stammt laut BND doch aus chinesischem Labor – Regierung hält Akten seit fünf Jahren geheim" [Reports: According to BND, Corona Comes from Chinese Lab – Government Has Kept Files Secret for Five Years], *Berliner Zeitung*, March 12, 2025, <https://www.berliner-zeitung.de/politik-gesellschaft/berichte-corona-stammt-laut-bnd-doch-aus-chinesischem-labor-regierung-haelt-akten-seit-5-jahren-geheim-li.2306480>.

acknowledged and elaborated on by Chinese scientists as recently as this year.^{15,16} He reviews the virus research interests of WIV researchers and their military collaborators. Many of these interests are related to public health or basic science research but some are dual use in nature. For example, Dr. Kadlec points out that there is historic precedent for developing neuro-incapacitating biological weapons and that Chinese military researchers have long written about achieving mental dominance in future military competition across the peacetime to warfighting continuum. He describes Chinese propaganda that portrays U.S. research in biodefense and cognitive enhancement as a threat to China. Although I think it is speculative that Covid was the product of military bioweapons research, Dr. Kadlec is not alone in his concerns that the Chinese military may be developing vaccines against novel coronaviruses that alter human cognition. In 2022, the House Permanent Select Committee on Intelligence (HPSCI's) minority staff wrote in their report that they are "aware of public and non-public information suggesting that SARS-CoV-2 may have been linked to China's bioweapons program."¹⁷ Their report highlighted that some Chinese military researchers subscribe to a worldview where other nations are developing coronaviruses as bioweapons and that such offensive pathogens could be passed off as naturally occurring. Nonetheless, it needs to be emphasized that there is still no credible evidence available to the public that substantiates a link between Covid and military bioweapons research.

After reading Dr. Kadlec's report, I feel that it is more important now than ever for the Chinese government to share the truth of how Covid began with the world. We need to defuse the vicious cycle of escalating threat perception that leads influential politicians and scientists to promote dual use research in fear of what other countries could be doing in secret. Even in 2025, I still hear some powerful voices arguing that gain-of-function research of concern is essential for national security and should not be subjected to more stringent regulation. After Covid, the risks of accidental release onto one's own population cannot be underestimated. It is not to the benefit of humanity or any major country to engage in antagonizing amounts of risky pathogen research for biodefense or national security purposes. Knowing how Covid originated will open the door to more precise and measured regulation of pathogen research, and likely go a long way to mitigate threat perception. In this regard, the Chinese government holds a unique power and responsibility to prevent an arms race by providing irrefutable evidence of Covid's origin.

About the Author

Dr. Alina Chan is a technology expert with experience in medical genetics, synthetic biology, and genetic engineering. She was a scientific advisor in the Broad Institute's vector engineering group, which modified non-pathogenic viruses to deliver gene therapies. She spearheaded the development of the COVID-19 CoV Genetics (covidcg.org) browser for scientists to

¹⁵ Alison Young (@alisonannyoung), "Study by researchers in China notes risk of accidental lab infections in BSL-2+ labs, the type historically used in that country for work with SARS-like coronaviruses...." X, August 20, 2025, <https://x.com/alisonannyoung/status/1958175188652003616>.

¹⁶ Yongxin Wang, "Personnel Exposure Studies to Multi-Source Diffusion of Bioaerosols Under Biosafety Laboratory - Level 2 Plus Operating Conditions," *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 495, (2025): 139076, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2025.139076>.

¹⁷ U.S. House of Representatives, Permanent Select Committee on Intelligence, *Unclassified Summary of the Second Interim Report on the Origins of the COVID-19 Pandemic*, 117th Cong., 2nd sess., 2022, Minority Views, https://intelligence.house.gov/uploadedfiles/final_unclass_summary_-_covid_origins_report_.pdf.

track variants and mutations across millions of viral genome sequences. In 2020, she advocated for an investigation into both natural and laboratory Covid-19 origin hypotheses and later published her work in a book, VIRAL: The Search for the Origin of Covid-19, and in the New York times. She co-founded the Bulletin of Atomic Scientists' taskforce in 2022 to generate cross-disciplinary recommendations to regulate risky pathogen research. Dr. Chan holds a Ph.D. in Biochemistry and Molecular Biology from the University of British Columbia.

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